

“TO BE” FE’LI XAQIDA

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Anotatsiya: "To Be" fe'li ingliz tilida eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan fe'llardan biri hisoblanadi. Ko'pgina qo'llanmalar ham aynan ana shu fe'lni o'rgatishdan boshlanadi. Men ham shu an'anani davom ettirgan holda, "to be" fe'lini dastlabki mavzu sifatida yoritmoqchiman. Maqolada "to be" fe'li haqida so'z yuritamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: to be, ko'plik, am, is, are, zamonlar.

1) "To be" fe'li ingliz tilidagi barcha fe'llar kabi bir xil funktsiyani bajaradi, ya'ni gapning kesimi bo'lib keladi. Masalan: to be - bo'lmoq, to have - ega bo'lmoq, to come - kelmoq, to tell - aytmoq. Biroq "to be" fe'lini fe'l zamonlarida qo'llaganimizda uning shakllaridan foydalanamiz.

2) Shunday qilib, Hozirgi noaniq zamonda 'to be' fe'lining 3 ta shakli mavjud: am, is, are. Quyidagi jadvalga e'tibor bering:

"To be" fe'lining shaxs-sonda tuslanishi

Shaxs-son Birlik Shaxs-son Ko'plik

1) I am 1) We are

2) You are 2) You are

3) He/She/It is 3) They are

Ko'rib turganingizdek, birinchi shaxs birlikda "am" ni ishlatamiz, ya'ni I am. Bu bilan siz tuzmoqchi bo'lgan gapingizni yarmini tuzib bo'ldingiz. Endi faqat "am" dan keyin keladigan so'zni qo'ysak bo'ldi. Masalan, biror kishini kasbini aytishda "to be" fe'lidan foydalanamiz. Demak, "I am a musician" deb aytishimiz mumkin. Jadvalni o'rganib chiqing va quyidagi gaplarni o'qing:

- I am a teacher - Men o'qituvchiman.
- You are tall - Sizning bo'yingiz baland.
- He is clever - U aqlli.
- She is 29 - U 29 yoshda.
- It is big - U katta.
- We are doctors - Bizlar shifokorlarmiz.
- They are students - Ular talabalar.

Quyida "to be" fe'lini qo'llash mumkin bo'lgan holatlar keltirilgan.2) "To be" fe'lining qo'llanilishi.

- am/is/are + kasblar: My father is a taxi-driver.
- am/is/are + sifatlar: She is very beautiful.
- am/is/are + sonlar: Anvar is 29 years old.
- this/that/these/those + is/are: This is a cat but that is a dog. These are computers but those are TV sets.

• There is/are: There are seven books on the table. There is box under the table. There are some bags behind the door.

Yuqorida to be fe'li yordamida bo'lishli gaplarni tuzishni o'rgandingiz. Shunday ekan quyidagi gaplarni tarjima qilishga harakat qiling.

Positive Sentences - Bo'lishli gaplar

I am a doctor. You are a bad student. He is a dentist. She is happy. It is cold today. We are at home. They are in the USA. You are good doctors. The cats are in the garden. Tom is ill today. The house is small. The nurse is an old woman.

Bo'lishli gaplardan tashqari inkor gaplar ham mavjud. Ularni yasash juda oson. "am/is/are" dan so'ng "not" so'zini yozsangiz kifoya. Demak: am not/ is not/ are not. Quyidagi gaplarni tarjima qilib ko'ring.

Negative Sentences - Inkor gaplar

She isn't my friend - U mening do'stim emas. They aren't here. I am not a fat girl. It isn't old. You aren't happy. He isn't at work. We aren't ready. It isn't big. My mother isn't old. The notebooks aren't on the desk. The man is not short.

So'roq gaplarni yasashda am/is/are ni gapning boshiga chiqarasiz. Berilgan gaplarni tarjima qiling.

Questions - So'roq gaplar Am I number 3? - Men 3 - raqammanmi? Is she your sister? Is it my bicycle? Are they at school? Is he a fat man? Aren't you doctors? Are we short? Isn't he ready? Is your father at home? Are Ted and Sam happy? Is your friend here?

